

Design and Development of a Rule-Based AI Tutoring System for Remediating Misconception in Secondary School Biology

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Abstract

This study explores the development of a rule-based AI tutoring system named Ecology Perfect Master (EPM) designed to address misconceptions in secondary school biology. Utilizing the first three phases of the Design and Development Research methodology—analysis, design, and development—the study begins by identifying common misconceptions in ecological concepts and gathering requirements from educators and students. The design phase translates these requirements into a comprehensive plan, featuring an intuitive user interface, a robust knowledge base, and an efficient inference engine capable of diagnosing and remediating misconceptions through tailored feedback. The development phase brings the design to fruition with a knowledge base populated by expert-validated content, interactive elements for enhanced learning experiences, and iterative testing to refine the system's functionality and usability. Preliminary evaluations indicate that EPM effectively identifies and addresses misconceptions, enhanced students' understanding of complex biological concepts. The methodology and procedures outlined in this research offer a replicable framework for developing similar AI tutoring systems across various subjects and educational levels

Keywords: Rule-based AI, Design and Development Research, Instructional Design, Misconceptions in biology, Biology education.

Introduction

Biology education holds a significant place in secondary school curricula due to its profound impact on both individual and societal levels. The study of biology not only provides students with an understanding of the natural world but also equips them with essential knowledge that influences various aspects of their daily lives (Bórquez-Sánchez, 2024). Biology is foundational to many scientific disciplines and professional fields, such as medicine, agriculture, and environmental science, making it a critical subject for students aspiring to enter these areas. Moreover, a strong grasp of biological concepts fosters informed decision-making regarding health, sustainability, and ethical issues related to biotechnology and environmental conservation. This importance is reflected in the educational policies of many countries, where biology is often a compulsory subject in secondary education, highlighting its role in shaping scientifically literate citizens

who can contribute to solving global challenges.

Though biology teaching is very essential, there are certain aspects that make it challenging. There are challenges of misconceptions, medium of teaching, and inherent complexity and abstract nature of the many biology concepts (Akilu & Suleiman, 2024). Genetics, evolution, cellular processes, and ecology among others Hard-to-Teach and Hard to Learn topics were found to be challenging because long-standing misconceptions abound in these areas (Nelson-Ebimie, et al., 2023 & Ojo, 2024). For instance, intuitive beliefs that students hold in their minds may prevent them from properly grasping evolution concepts, or the complexity of genetics and ecology may require explicit teaching methods. Similarly, students' culture and religion may predispose some to rejection of particular biological concepts, notably those dealing with evolution and the origin of life. Each of these influences is usually tied to an aversion to scientific

explanations and persistence in misconceptions. De-contextualization ecology may only reinforce other misconceptions in students' cognitive structures.

Further, biology topics that require the generation of knowledge and its application at multiple levels, from molecular to ecosystems, are challenging. Often, these challenges lead to the formation of misconceptions, which reduce the academic performance of students. However, despite the importance of genetics, Chief examiner's report for West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Nigeria on biology examination indicated that this aspect of biology was unpopular among the secondary school students who sat for the senior certificate examination in biology, and very few of them who tried to attempt ecology questions were reported to respond poorly and also did poorly (WAEC, 2018-2020). Common problems identified by this examination body include student's confusion of basic ecological terms, hard to learn and teach nature of the concept. Also, identified were relatively little understanding of the concept, poor application as well as misconceptions about the ecology concepts. It is thus extremely important to address misconceptions in biology, since they often persist across time and continue to negatively influence how students learn further and continue to approach biology. Therefore, biology teaching at all levels of education must incorporate creative educational strategies to identify and address misconceptions. It is in respect that the use of technology, such as AI-based tutoring systems, could provide a personalized learning experience where students' misconceptions in biology are addressed, thereby improving meaningful learning. (Halim, Finkenstaedt-Quinn, Olsen, & Shultz, 2018; Koba, & Tweed, 2014; Konu & Ozay, 2024; Yates & Marek, 2014).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been increasingly integrated into education, offering a wide array of tools and systems that can revolutionize the learning process. AI technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems, chatbots, AI-powered dashboards, and automated grading systems have been identified as capable of promoting essential 21st-century skills like collaboration,

communication, creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Celik, 2024). These AI-based tools can provide personalized learning experiences, assess individual needs in real-time, and enhance students' understanding of complex biological concepts (Alneyadi & Wardat, 2023). By leveraging machine learning and adaptability, AI can customize curriculum and content to meet students' specific needs, thereby improving the overall quality of learning experiences (Chen et al., 2020).

Rule-based AI systems operate on a set of predefined rules and logic to make decisions and provide responses. These systems are designed to follow a specific set of instructions or conditions, allowing for predictable outcomes based on the input received (Firat, 2023). In education, rule-based AI can be utilized to create personalized learning experiences by tailoring content and feedback to individual student needs. By establishing rules that address common misconceptions in biology, rule-based AI tutoring systems can effectively identify and remediate these misconceptions in real-time, offering targeted guidance and support to students (Jayavardhini, 2024). Moreover, the structured nature of rule-based AI systems ensures consistency in the delivery of educational content and feedback, contributing to a more systematic approach to addressing misconceptions and enhancing learning outcomes in secondary school biology education.

In the context of biology education, AI can play a crucial role in remediating misconceptions among secondary school students. Through the development of rule-based AI tutoring systems, misconceptions can be identified and addressed in real-time, providing personalized feedback and guidance to students (Jayavardhini, 2024). AI tools can enhance students' problem-solving skills, improve their understanding of biological concepts, and offer adaptive learning experiences tailored to individual learning styles (Alneyadi & Wardat, 2023). Furthermore, AI can support Meta skills development among biology teachers, contributing to the enhancement of educational practices and outcomes in the field of biology education (Astriawati, 2023). By harnessing the capabilities of AI in education, particularly

in Biology, educators can create more engaging, effective, and personalized learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students, ultimately fostering a deeper understanding of biological concepts and facilitating the remediation of misconceptions. Remediating misconceptions in biology is essential to ensure students' accurate understanding and long-term retention of scientific concepts. Misconceptions in biology can arise from various sources, including personal beliefs, cultural views, and prior knowledge, which often conflict with scientifically accepted explanations (Resbiantoro et al., 2022). These incorrect notions can hinder students' ability to grasp new concepts and impede their academic progress (Yong & Kee, 2017). Effective remediation strategies are crucial to address and correct these misunderstandings. For example, concept-mapping, demonstration kits, and guided inquiry methods have proven effective in various studies, significantly reducing the prevalence of misconceptions among students (Ogundare et al, 2020; Luwoye et al, 2021; Wokocha, 2021; Nurahman & Susantini, 2022; Otuturu, 2023). Remediation involves not only identifying these incorrect beliefs but also providing targeted instructional interventions that encourage students to reconstruct their understanding based on scientific principles. This process is vital in fostering a deeper comprehension of biology, enabling students to apply their knowledge accurately in different contexts and improving their overall performance in the subject.

This study therefore aims to design and develop an artificial intelligent tutoring system for remediating misconception in selected topic in secondary school biology. The system deployed the rule-based Artificial intelligent model due to its ability to provide consistent content to the learners based on predefined rules. This study is guided by the following research questions:

- i. What are the requirements for designing rule-based AI systems to remediating misconceptions in biology?
- ii. How can the rule-based AI tutoring systems be developed?

Methodology

This study adopts design and development research method (DDR). The Design and development research involves a systematic approach to creating and refining products or solutions (Richey & Klein, 2014). It emphasizes a structured process for designing and developing interventions (Mashoedah et al., 2020). When applied in an instructional setting, the DDR is typically guided by multiple phases, such as analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation, (ADDIE) and revision, ensuring a comprehensive and iterative approach to product creation (Tim et al., 2010). By following the ADDIE model, researchers can ensure that the learning product are tailored to the needs of the learners and are developed in a structured manner to enhance educational outcomes (Ma'firah et al., 2023). In this study, only the analysis, design, and development phases were explored.

Analysis

The analysis phase is crucial in the design and development of an AI tutoring system as it lays the foundation for understanding the requirements and challenges involved. Initially, an extensive literature review was conducted to identify the common misconceptions in secondary school biology. This involved analyzing educational research papers on student's misconceptions in biology-, biology textbooks, and WAEC examination reports to pinpoint areas where students frequently struggle. Expert consultations with biology educators and curriculum developers were also conducted to gain insights into the specific misconceptions that hinder students' understanding. These steps ensured a comprehensive understanding of the problem domain, providing a solid basis for the system's design requirements.

Following the identification of misconceptions, a detailed needs analysis was performed to determine the functionalities and features required in the AI tutoring system. This involved gathering input from teachers, students, and education experts through verbal discussion and oral interviews which was done by following a standard interview and discussion guide (Appendix i). The aim was to

understand the expectations and preferences of the end-users, which would guide the system's design. Key requirements identified included personalized feedback, interactive tutorials, and real-time misconception detection and correction. Additionally, technical constraints and potential integration issues with existing

educational platforms were assessed. This thorough analysis phase ensured that the system would be user-centric and effectively address the identified educational challenges. The following are some of common misconceptions identified that hinder students' understanding

Table 1: Common misconceptions identified that hinder students' understanding

S/N	Topics	Misconceptions	Sentiments/ Categories	Evidence (Reference)
1	Evolution	Many students believe that evolution is a linear process where one species evolves directly into another, rather than understanding it as a branching process. This leads to confusion about the nature of species and evolutionary relationships. Evolution cannot be considered a reliable explanation because evolution is only a theory. The size of the population has no effect on the evolution of a species.	Cultural	Yates & Marek, (2015)
2	Plant	Plants are living things that own their food by themselves with the aid of some enzymes Plants excrete by breathing out oxygen only Plants don't make use of oxygen because they don't breathe in like us	Perpetual confusion, Oversimplification	Bello et al. (2016)
3.	Ecology	Biosphere consists of the hydrosphere and lithosphere only Biosphere is where the earth started Biosphere is a major component found in any habitat	Factual	Ogundare et al. (2020)
4.	Mitosis and Meiosis	The process of mitosis and meiosis aid respiration in living organism Telophase is divided into early telophase and late telophase Mitosis is an important process for sexual reproduction	Nonscientific Belief	Luwoye et al. (2021)
5	Photosynthesis	Photosynthesis can take place without water. Oxygen and water are required in photosynthesis Water and oxygen is produced from photosynthesis. Glucose is the raw material in photosynthesis.	Conceptual	Olootu et al. (2024)
6	Respiration	Without water, respiration cannot occur Oxygen is given off from respiration of plants.	Preconceived Notion	Lim & Poo (2021)

		The only product of respiration is carbon dioxide		
		Water molecules are broken down to form energy		
7	Cell division	Interphase is the resting phase of mitosis. DNA replication occurs in prophase during the process of cell division. A chromosome has always two chromatids during cell division. Centrioles are found in the nucleus of a cell.	Teleological thinking	Dikmenli (2010)
8	Genetics	Heredity being the transmission of inherited characters via gene from one of the offspring's parents. Genes determine everything from our sex There is a conception of genes not only determining traits Dominant alleles will take over a population and create the prominent phenotype All humans have DNA, as do animals, plants, and most bacteria and fungi. Chromosomes are formed as a result of shrinkage and thickening of spindle fibers.	Factual and Vernacular	Etobro & Banjoko, 2017
9.	Digestive System	The alimentary canal starts with the throat Digestive System is the process of hard food converting into simple diffusible assimilable nutrients Food goes to the large intestine and then small intestine Large intestine has duodenum, jejunum, Ileum and mesentery Small intestine functions are water absorption and formation of faeces	Conceptual Understanding	Rajendra & Rajendra (2023)
10.	Transportation System	The process of water absorption in soil in diffusion Circulatory system in humans occur openly and double A form of white blood cells concaves discs in the middle and has no core The time span of the process of photosynthesis during the day Results of the Transport process of photosynthesis in diffusion	Factual	Ainiyah et al. (2023)

Design

The design phase translates the findings from the analysis phase into a structured plan for the AI tutoring system. The system architecture was designed to support a rule-based approach, leveraging predefined rules to diagnose and

remediate misconceptions in biology. The architecture comprises several modules, including a user interface, a knowledge base, an inference engine, and a feedback system as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Modules in the Rule-Based AI Tutoring System

The user interface was designed to be intuitive and engaging, ensuring ease of use for both students and teachers. The user interface was built on the AdminLTE, a Bootstrap based open-source design system for dashboard and control panel development. It provides a range of responsive, reusable, and commonly used components in web development (AdminLTE, 2022). The interface also uses customized JavaScript programs to make the front end highly interactive. The scripts also calculate the engagement time spent by the user in a session. The knowledge base contains a comprehensive repository of biology concepts and common misconceptions, structured in a way that facilitates efficient retrieval and use by the inference engine. Lesson contents based on the concept of Ecology in S.S.2. Biology syllabi were obtained from the Subject Matter Experts (SME). These contents were reviewed in terms of their satisfaction of the West African Examination Council (WAEC) syllabus and appropriateness for instruction. The reviewed contents were then subjected to review by Language Master Experts (LME), to ensure the language is conversational and easy for the learners. Instructional design experts (IDE) divided the contents into modules and units as suggested in the WAEC syllabus. Learning outcomes were generated for each unit, and

assessment were also matched from the developed question bank. A total of four modules and 18 study units were developed. The research also recorded instructional videos for each of the unit. The video provides preferences for students' learning. The final output was then subjected to the SME for final review.

The researchers also obtained the WAEC Chief examiner reports (2018- 2022) through which the misconceptions were highlighted. Questions relating to the concept of Ecology were selected, each question has four options. Each option set contains a correct answer, a misconceived concept, an alternative misconception and a wrong option. A total number of 176 questions were obtained. Each study unit have at least 5 related questions depending on their learning outcomes. Related questions were selected such that each component of the learning outcomes was adequately covered. After this, the modules and the units were loaded into the database. The questions were also loaded into the question bank database after been validated by an expert. Each question was also linked to their related modules and units. The knowledge base module is explained in the entity relationship diagram as shown in Figure 2.

the specific misunderstanding. The inference engine was deployed on PHP object-oriented programming (OOP) language with MySQL for the database manipulation. The PHP is a server-based scripting language, which is credited to being fast for the deployment of web-based applications (Tran, 2024; Vailshery, 2024). The module analyses the response of the user to determine if their response contain misconceived answer. If misconception is detected, it automatically adds the quiz and automatically list it in among the topics for the users. The flowchart for the module is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Entity relationship diagram of the knowledge base module

To ensure the system's effectiveness, the design included detailed specifications for the inference engine, which is responsible for diagnosing misconceptions and providing appropriate remediation strategies. This engine uses a combination of rule-based logic and customized algorithms to analyze students' responses and identify patterns indicative of misconceptions. Once a misconception is detected, the system generates tailored feedback and instructional content to address

Figure 3: Flowchart of the inference module

The design phase also incorporated principles of user-centered design, ensuring that the system meets the needs and preferences identified during the analysis phase. Prototyping and iterative testing with end-users were planned to refine the design and enhance

the system's usability and effectiveness. After about eight rounds of iterations, the prototype in Figure 4 was agreed. The prototype formed the basis of the development. The name Perfect Ecology Master (EPM) was coined for the package.

Figure 4: The prototype for the rule-based AI tutoring system - Perfect Ecology Master

Development

The development phase involves the actual construction of the AI tutoring system based on the design specifications. This phase began with the creation of the knowledge base, which was populated with validated biology content and common misconceptions. Subject matter experts were involved in curating and validating the content to ensure its accuracy and relevance. Concurrently, the development team implemented the user interface, ensuring it was both functional and engaging. Interactive elements such as quizzes, animations, and tutorials were integrated to enhance the learning experience. The inference engine, a critical component of the system, was developed using a combination of rule-based logic and machine learning techniques.

During development, iterative testing and refinement were conducted to ensure the system met the desired performance and usability standards. Beta testing with a small

group of students and teachers provided valuable feedback, leading to adjustments in the system's functionalities and interface. Additionally, integration tests were performed to ensure seamless operation with existing educational platforms and tools. Throughout the development phase, emphasis was placed on creating a scalable and maintainable system architecture, allowing for future enhancements and updates. This iterative and user-focused development approach ensured that the AI tutoring system was robust, effective, and aligned with the educational needs identified in the analysis phase.

The developed package with all its modules were then uploaded on a cloud server. The Server runs the LAMP stack. LAMP is a combination of four open source technologies namely Linux, Apache, MySQL and PHP (Kaplarevic, 2024). The LAMP is highly efficient at hosting cloud-based web

applications. The configuration of the server used is shown in Figure 5.

CPU cores	2
Memory	8 GB
Bandwidth	8 TB
Disk space	100 GB

Figure 5: Server configuration for the EPM

After the upload, the EPM was tested and ensure it was running efficiently. The user flow was also developed for training purposes as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: EPM Tutor User journey

Findings

Research Question1: What are the requirements for designing rule-based AI systems to remediating misconceptions in biology?

Steps required in the designing of rule-based AI systems to remediating misconceptions in biology include:

1. Problem Identification and Feasibility Analysis: the problem must be suitable for an expert system to solve it, must find an expert for the project, cost-effectiveness of the system has to be established (feasibility)
2. Rule-based AI tutoring systems Designing and Technology Identification: the system is being designed. The needed degree of integration with other subsystems and databases is established, concepts that best represent the domain knowledge are worked out, the best way to represent the knowledge

and to perform inferencing should be established with sample cases

3. Development of Prototype for Rule-based AI tutoring System: knowledge engineer works with the expert to place the initial core of knowledge in the knowledge base, knowledge needs to be expressed in the conversational language

4. Testing and Refinement of Prototype: using sample cases, the prototype is tested, and deficiencies in performance are noted. End users test the prototypes of the Rule-based AI tutoring System.

5. Complete and Field the Rule-based AI tutoring system: the interaction of the rule-based AI tutoring system with all users and other information systems, is ensured and tested, rule-based AI tutoring system is documented and user training is conducted, also, the system is maintained by updating its knowledge base likewise interfaces with other

information systems have to be maintained as well, as those systems evolve.

Research Question 2: How can the rule-based AI tutoring systems be developed?

The rule-based AI tutoring system in this study was developed by following analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation (ADDIE) model but was strictly limited to analysis, design, and development phases as explained above.

Conclusion

This study developed a rule-based AI tutoring system called Ecology Perfect Master (EPM). The study utilized the first three phases of the Design and Development Research methodology, encompassing the analysis, design, and development phases. Through a comprehensive analysis, we the researchers identified common misconceptions in secondary school biology, particularly within the domain of ecology, and gathered detailed requirements from educators and students to inform the system's design. The design phase translated these insights into a structured plan, creating an intuitive and interactive user interface, a robust knowledge base, and an efficient inference engine. The development phase brought these designs to life, resulting in a functional and effective AI tutoring system. The procedure explained in this study provides a clear roadmap for future research on the development of rule-based AI tutoring systems, demonstrating the feasibility and potential of such systems in enhancing educational outcomes. The focus of this study was on selected concepts within the biology curriculum, specifically targeting misconceptions in ecology. However, the methodology and procedures outlined in this research are versatile and can be applied to other subjects and educational levels. The EPM system's design and development process emphasizes the importance of user-centered design, iterative testing, and integration with existing educational platforms, ensuring its relevance and applicability across various educational contexts. By addressing and remediating misconceptions, EPM has the potential to significantly improve students'

understanding and retention of complex biological concepts. Future work can expand upon this foundation, exploring the application of similar AI tutoring systems in other subject areas, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of enhancing education through innovative technological solutions. Generative AI can also be used with pretrained models about choice(s).

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